
Bridging the Divide: Analyzing Income and Wealth Inequality in India for Inclusive Growth

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Introduction:

Inequality can be seen from different perspectives. Most common metric is income and wealth inequality, which refers to the extent to which income is evenly distributed within a population. In India, income and wealth inequality have been a persistent challenge, which reflects deep structural problem of the country's socio-economic ailment. Despite noteworthy economic growth have been achieved, the benefits have not been equitably distributed among the population of the country. As per the world Bank, India's Gini Index is 35.2 (0.35) as of March 2020 remains highest in the world, reflecting a huge gap between the rich and poor. This picture shows broad idea of the human society and its disparity, where majority of the people lacks from their basic necessities. Therefore, it is necessary to explore the scale and trends of inequality in India, the factors driving it, and its implications for economic stability.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the conceptual framework of Inequality.
2. To overview the income and wealth inequality in Indian perspective.

Conceptual Framework:

Income and wealth inequality refer to the uneven distribution of financial resources and assets among individuals or groups within a society. While these two concepts are closely related, they address

different aspects of economic disparity. Income inequality refers to the disparity in earnings among individuals and households in the society. While the term wealth inequality refers to disparities in the distribution of assets and net worth of the individuals or households. For measuring the income inequality, the metrics like Gini coefficient, income share ratios or Lorenz curves are used.

Wage gaps between high and low-skilled workers, unequal opportunities or access to education facilities, highly automation in industry and service sector etc. are causes for income inequality. Income disparities often lead to wealth disparities over time. And other side wealth provides additions income streams which reinforcing the cycle of inequality.

Inequality in Income and wealth at Globe:

Global income and wealth inequality remains persistent problem. As per the data of world bank the number of economies tracks with high inequality. These are defined with a Gini index based on income and consumption from household survey. The recent household survey data, 49 countries of the world where approximately 22 percent population lives, had a Gini index over 40. Nearly half of the world's wealth is concentrated in the hands of the top 1 percent of the richest individuals. The wealth of many billionaires is equivalent to

the combined of millions of lower-income individuals. As of 2023, the 26 wealthiest billionaires in the world controlled a staggering \$2.872 trillion, as reported by the latest UBS Global Wealth Report. To put this into perspective, their combined fortune surpasses the annual economic output of most countries, based on World Bank GDP data. Globalization, technological change, labour market trends, tax and social policies etc. are the key drivers of global disparities.

Income and wealth inequality in India:

India has been lauded by the President of the World Economic Forum, who envisions the country will reach at \$10 trillion economy near future. While India's economic growth is undoubtedly gaining momentum, the benefits of this progress aren't reaching everyone, particularly those who are marginalized. According to the data published by Govt. of India, inequality declined post-independence till the 1980s,

but it began rising from 1991 and has hit the roof after 2014s. After independence India adopted social democracy and framed the economic policies for inclusive growth while opposing the perceived inequalities and monopolies. Inequality in both rural and urban areas has widened significantly between 2012-13 and 2022-23, as the report of National Sample Survey Office. By the end of 2022-23, the wealth and income share of the top 1 % reached a historical high of 40.1%. Another report reveals that the wealthiest 1 % of Indian now hold 58 percent of the country's wealth and the top 10 percent control a staggering 80 percent while poorer half of the population struggles to hold onto a mere 4.1 percent of the nation's wealth. This trend has consistently increased, it means richer are getting rich much faster than the poor. It causes widening the income gap and shows the failure of economic policies.

Table 1: Income inequality in India, 2022-23

Income Group	Income Share (%)	Average Income	Ratio to Average
Average	100.0	2,34,551	1.0
Bottom 50 %	15.0	71,163	0.3
Middle 40 %	27.3	1,05,413	0.7
Top 10 %	57.7	13,52,985	5.8
Top 1 %	22.6	20,73,846	22.6
Top 0.1 %	9.6	2,24,58,442	95.8
Top 0.01 %	4.3	10,18,14,669	434.1
Top 0.001%	2.1	20,01,98,548	2,068.6

Source: 1) Combining national income accounts aggregates, tax tabulations and surveys on income and consumption. 2) Income and wealth inequality in India: 1922-2023, Nitin Kumar Bharati, Lucas Chancel, Thomas Piketty, Anmol Somanchi

The table presents income distribution in India in 2022-23, all INR values in current 2022 prices. This table presents an analysis of income distribution, highlighting disparities across income groups. The average income is set as the baseline for comparison with a ratio of 1.0. It is seen as stark disparity between income groups, particularly between the lower 50 percent and top earners.

The bottom 50 percent income group hold just 15 percent of total income. Average income of this group is 71,163

rupees, which is only 30 percent of the average income and in ratio it is 0.3. The income share of the middle is 27.3 percent and ratio to average income is 0.7. Top ten percent control 57.7 percent of the total income, the ratio of the average income of this group is 5.8 times to the national average income. Top 1% alone command 22.6% of the total income, which is equal the combined share of the bottom 50 %. Average income was 22.6 times greater than national average national income. Top 0.001 % command 2.1 % of the national income.

Average income of this group is over 20 crore which is 2068.6 times high than national average income. This group

epitomizes ultra-high net worth individuals, highlighting the apex of income inequality.

Table 2: Wealth inequality in India, 2022-23

Income Group	Wealth Share (%)	Average Wealth	Ratio to Average
Average	100.0	13,49,029	1.0
Bottom 50 %	6.4	1,73,184	0.1
Middle 40 %	28.6	9,63,560	0.7
Top 10 %	65.0	87,70,132	6.5
Top 1 %	40.1	5,41,41,525	40.1
Top 0.1 %	29.7	40,04,54,807	296.8
Top 0.01 %	22.2	2,99,67,73,491	2,221.4
Top 0.001%	16.8	22,61,33,54,928	16,762.7

Source: 1) *Combining national income accounts aggregates, tax tabulations and surveys on income and consumption.* 2) *Income and wealth inequality in India: 1922-2023, Nitin Kumar Bharati, Lucas Chancel, Thomas Piketty, Anmol Somanchi*

This table provides an overview of the distribution of wealth among different income groups, highlighting extreme inequalities. In India, top 0.001 percent people holds 16.8 percent of total wealth. This is an elite group with an average wealth of 2.2 thousand crore rupees, making them 16,762.7 times wealthier than the average person. Top 1 percent richer controls 40.1 percent while top 10 percent wealthier accumulated 65 percent of total wealth.

Bottom 50 percent holds only 6.4 percent of total wealth, with an average wealth significantly below the overall average which was 0.1 times the average. In case of middle 40 percent population holding 28.6 percent of wealth. Their wealth levels were approximately 0.7 times the overall average, indicating a moderate share of resource. This group represents a broader middle class. It was examined from the above table that wealth becoming increasingly concentrated as we ascend the income pyramid.

The concentration of wealth in the hands of some people has been passed down from generation to generation, which has perpetuated inequality, as the rich pass on the benefits of their wealth to their descendants.

Property inheritance right, inadequate land reforms, crony capitalism,

skewed distribution of economic gains, regressive taxation policies, lack of society safety net and welfare programs, wage gaps, caste discrimination, gender inequality, lack of access to education, technological deprivation etc. are the major causes for income and wealth inequality.

Various measures have been implemented to address inequality by the Government of India. These measures are focused on inclusive growth, social justice and empowerment of human. The key initiatives are as; Income redistribution through taxation, Employment Generation Programs like Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA), Skill India Mission, Start-up and Stand-up India, Mudra Yojana, Right to Education, National Food Security Act (NFSA), Reservation Policies, Financial Inclusion Policies.

For improving the lives of the people and aiming to reduce poverty in all dimensions, Govt. of India has made remarkable progress with various programmes and policies. The programmes like Poshan Aahar, Anemia Mukta Bharat, Targeted Public Distribution System under National Food Security Act, Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana etc. have made significant contribution to uplift the life of poor. According the data published by the

Govt., Public Distribution System covers 81.35 crore beneficiaries which is world's largest food security programme. The programmes like maternal health, clean cooking fuel distribution through Ujjwala Yojana, improved electricity coverage via Saubhagya, and transformative campaigns like Swachh Bharat Mission and Jal Jeevan Mission have collectively elevated living conditions and overall well-being of people.

While the performance of States varies, some States which were traditionally having high poverty have made remarkable progress in helping people escape poverty, thus reducing inter-state disparities in multidimensional poverty. With this, the fundamental problems in accessing basic services are getting resolved fast so that the country can look towards becoming a developed nation. The measures for reducing inequality in India have made significant impression upto 1990s which assisted boosting consumption and aggregate demand, improved the earning capacity of rural households. The number of billionaires in India has grown significantly after 1991, yet the disparity between income and wealth has widened at an alarming pace since 2014. For India to realize its dream of becoming a global superpower, it is imperative to focus on inclusive development, ensuring that prosperity reaches every stratum of society.

Conclusion:

Income and wealth inequality in India reflects deep-rooted structural challenges despite the country's notable economic growth and various government measures intended at reducing disparities. The stark figures of income and wealth concentration among the top 1% and the bottom 50% highlight a critical imbalance that continues to widen.

While India's economic growth places it on the path to becoming a global superpower, the benefits have largely remained concentrated in the hands of a few. Wealth inheritance, limited access to quality education, inadequate redistributive policies

etc. have worsened disparity. The persistence of such disparities hampers social cohesion and poses challenges to sustainable development.

The government has introduced numerous initiatives aimed at fostering inclusive growth, such as MGNREGA, financial inclusion programs and social security schemes. These measures have improved access to basic necessities and consumption of the society. However, the rapid pace at which wealth is accumulating among the top earners (Billionaires) indicates the need for a more equitable redistribution framework.

To achieve a balanced and inclusive growth model, India must address basic causes of inequality through comprehensive policies focusing on education, skill development, progressive taxation and social welfare programs. By bridging this disparity can India ensure that its economic prosperity benefits all sections of society and realize its vision of becoming a truly developed nation.

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